

A direct FE^2 method for concurrent multilevel modeling of composites

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FE² : Introduction

- Used for the analysis of structures from heterogeneous materials
- No need for constitutive relation for heterogeneous material
- Comprises two levels of Finite Element (FE) simulations :
 - Macroscale level : structure is discretized into homogenized continuum finite elements
 - Microscale level : RVEs where the different phases of the heterogeneous material are explicitly modeled
- Iterative exchange of information between two scales
 - Macro → Micro : Kinematic constraints
 - Micro → Macro : Homogenized stress

FE² : Introduction

A typical FE² analysis

(R.J.M. Smit, W.A.M. Brekelmans, H.E.H. Meijer, 1998)

Direct FE² method

- Hill-Mandel condition is invoked to collapse macro- and microscale FE simulations into a single microscale FE simulation
- Kinematic constraints maps loads on macroscale structure to forces on the microscale FE mesh
- Why Direct FE² ?
 - Eliminates need for control code to handle information exchange between 2 scales
 - Runs on commercial FE codes as a single analysis
 - MPCs are imposed at pre-processing stage; no user-defined subroutines required for FE analysis
 - Features already on commercial codes (e.g., finite deformation, viscoplasticity, damage models) remain available without any user intervention

Derivation

FEM

$$\sigma_{ij,j} + b_i = 0$$

$$\int_V \delta u_{i,j} \sigma_{ij} dV = \int_V \delta u_i b_i dV + \int_s \delta u_i t_i ds$$

$$\sum_e \sum_\alpha (w_\alpha J_\alpha \delta u_{i,j}(\mathbf{x}_\alpha) \sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_\alpha))_e = f_I \delta d_I$$

$$\cancel{K_{IJ} d_J \delta d_I} = \cancel{f_I \delta d_I}$$

Direct FE²

$$\sum_e \sum_\alpha (w_\alpha J_\alpha \langle \delta \tilde{u}_{i,j} \rangle_\alpha \langle \tilde{\sigma}_{ij} \rangle_\alpha)_e = f_I \delta d_I$$

$$\sum_e \sum_\alpha \left(\frac{w_\alpha J_\alpha}{V_\alpha} \int_{V_\alpha} \delta \tilde{u}_{i,j} \tilde{\sigma}_{ij} dV \right)_e = f_I \delta d_I$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_\alpha = w_\alpha J_\alpha \\ d_I = L_{IH} \tilde{d}_H \end{array} \right.$$

$$\sum_e \sum_\alpha \left(\int_{V_\alpha} \delta \tilde{u}_{i,j} \tilde{\sigma}_{ij} dV \right)_e = f_I L_{IH} \delta \tilde{d}_H$$

$$\cancel{\tilde{K}_{HJ} \tilde{d}_J \delta \tilde{d}_H} = \cancel{\tilde{f}_H \delta \tilde{d}_H}$$

Results

Comparison of Force vs Displacement predictions for finite deformation of homogeneous and CFRP cantilever beams

*** more results will be shown during oral presentation ...

Conclusions

- FE² simulations allows for the analyses of structures made from heterogeneous materials without the need for homogenized material models
- Direct FE² reduces the two separate and concurrent simulations at macro- and mirco-scales required in FE² to a single simulation
- Direct FE² can be carried out on directly on commercial FE codes
- Features already on commercial codes (e.g., finite deformation, viscoplasticity, damage models) remain available without any user intervention

THANK YOU

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